

STRENGTH PREDICTION OF COMPRESSIVE LOADED LAMINATES CONTAINING CIRCULAR HOLES

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ABSTRACT

The Damage Zone Criterion (DZC) is used to predict the in-plane compressive strength of laminates containing circular holes. The DZC assumes a damaged zone in the maximum stress region of the laminate when the compressive stress reaches the compressive strength of the unnotched laminate. Taking into account the stress redistribution followed by a damage development, a closed form analytical expression of the strength is derived from the equilibrium conditions of the specimen. The strength of laminates with circular holes is then predicted on the basis of two fundamental parameters, the unnotched compressive strength (σ_{oc}) and the critical damage zone length (d_{IC}^*). An experimental program is conducted to determine the criterion parameters and validate the criterion. Good agreement was found between experiment and model results.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Graphite/Epoxy; Compression; Holes; Failure Criterion.

1. INTRODUCTION

From a macroscopic point of view, Lessard [1] suggested that the failure of laminated composites which contain holes and are subjected to unidirectional compressive loads be divided into three categories (Figure 1): (a) elastic laminate buckling (Euler buckling) related to geometric instability; (b) sublaminar buckling or buckling of a ply or group of plies; and (c) damage* due to in-plane forces.

These failure modes have been investigated separately in the literature. Many investigators [1-11] have studied the in-plane failure of composite laminates which contained circular holes and were loaded in compression. A majority of these studies [2-8] have reported

*Damage refers to the collective effect on the material of micromechanical failure modes such as fiber buckling and/or fiber shear crippling involving fiber kinking [10].

good results by extending the concept of the characteristic distance approach to predict the strength. Chang et al. [9] developed a progressive damage zone model to predict the in-plane compressive strength of laminated composites containing open holes, and reported good agreement between the test results and the the model predictions.

Recently, a new criterion called the Damage Zone Criterion, DZC, was proposed for tensile loaded laminates containing holes and slits [12]. The objective of the present study was to extend the concept of the DZC to predict the in-plane strength of compressive loaded laminates containing circular holes.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider a laminated composite plate (gauge length l , width w , and thickness t) made from fiber-reinforced unidirectional plies, containing a circular hole with diameter d located at the center of the plate, as shown in Figure 2. The ply orientations are selected from the four basic directions (0, 90, +45, and -45-degrees), which are defined in the figure. The ply orientations are symmetric and balanced* with respect to the z -plane (middle surface). The geometry of the specimen may be chosen arbitrarily, but the thickness must be small relative to the width and length.

The laminate is subjected to an in-plane compressive load P . During loading, the plate deforms in its own plane until failure occurs, at which point the plate cannot sustain any additional load. The load at this point is defined as failure load.

3. THE DAMAGE ZONE CRITERION

During increasing loading of a laminate with a hole, a damage zone forms and grows in the most stress-intense region at the edge of the hole (Figure 3). "Damage" includes the collective effects on the material of micromechanical failure mechanisms.

In the unloaded material, there is no damage. When the load is increased so that the compressive stress at the edge of the hole reaches the compressive strength of the unnotched laminate, σ_{oc} , a damage zone is assumed to start forming (Figure 3b).

The actual damage zone, which in reality has a two dimensional extension (three dimensional if the thickness direction is included) is represented along or projected onto the net-section plane (Figure 4). For simplicity, a constant stress distribution was assumed within the damage zone. The stress distribution, σ_y^* , ahead of the damage zone is assumed to have the same shape as the linear elastic stress distribution, σ_y . Note that, for reasons of equilibrium, σ_y^* is in a different location than σ_y .

The hole diameter is $2R$, the specimen width w , the thickness of the plate t , and the critical length of the damage zone d_{IC}^* . The applied stress is σ_N and the difference between σ_y^* and σ_y is $\Delta\sigma^*$, which is given by:

$$\Delta\sigma^* = \sigma_{oc} - \sigma_y (R + d_{IC}^*) \quad (1)$$

*Equal number of +45- and -45-degree plies.

The strength of the specimen is derived from the equilibrium conditions. The applied load is in equilibrium with the axial force acting on the net-section plane:

$$\sigma_{oc} d_{IC}^* t + \int_{R+d_{IC}^*}^{w/2} (\sigma_y + \Delta\sigma^*) t dx = \sigma_N \frac{w}{2} t \quad (2)$$

3.1 Derived Strength of Specimens with Circular Holes The strength of specimens containing circular holes (CH-specimens) was derived from Eq. (2) using the linear elastic stress distribution, σ_y , along the net-section plane (x -axis) for an infinite orthotropic plate containing an open circular hole of radius R [13]:

$$\sigma_y = \frac{\sigma_N}{2} \left\{ 2 + \left(\frac{R}{x} \right)^2 + 3 \left(\frac{R}{x} \right)^4 - (K^\infty - 3) \left[5 \left(\frac{R}{x} \right)^6 - 7 \left(\frac{R}{x} \right)^8 \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

The stress concentration factor of the subject material for an infinite plate, K^∞ , is given by [14]:

$$K^\infty = 1 + \left[\frac{2}{A_{22}} \left(\sqrt{A_{11}A_{22}} - A_{12} + \frac{A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2}{2A_{66}} \right) \right]^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where A_{ij} are the orthotropic in-plane stiffnesses of the laminate. No finite width correction was used in Eq.(3). It was assumed that the width has only a minor effect on the the shape of the stress distribution.

The ratio of notched to unnotched strength for a CH-specimen, from Eqs. (1), (2), and (3), is:

$$\frac{\sigma_N}{\sigma_{oc}} = \frac{w - 2R}{w - m_2 + m_3 + m_1 \left[\frac{w}{2} - R - d_{IC}^* \right]} \quad (5)$$

where

$$m_1 = 2 + \left(\frac{R}{p} \right)^2 + 3 \left(\frac{R}{p} \right)^4 - (K^\infty - 3) \left[5 \left(\frac{R}{p} \right)^6 - 7 \left(\frac{R}{p} \right)^8 \right] \quad (6)$$

$$m_2 = 2q - \frac{R^2}{q} - \frac{R^4}{q^3} + (K^\infty - 3) \left[\frac{R^6}{q^5} - \frac{R^8}{q^7} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$m_3 = 2p - \frac{R^2}{p} - \frac{R^4}{p^3} + (K^\infty - 3) \left[\frac{R^6}{p^5} - \frac{R^8}{p^7} \right] \quad (8)$$

and

$$p = R + d_{IC}^* \quad (9)$$

$$q = w/2 \quad (10)$$

4. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF THE CRITERION

4.1 Specimen Preparation and Testing Experiments were performed to determine the parameters used in the DZC, and to generate data which was used to validate the criterion.

Specimens (Figure 5) were fabricated from the toughened graphite/epoxy HTA7/6376 system, which is commercially available from Ciba-Geigy. Three different laminates (A,

B, and C) with configurations as shown in Table 1 were processed and ultrasonically inspected to detect processing related flaws. The laminates proved of good quality. Three specimens of each laminate configuration and geometry were fabricated.

The fixture used is shown schematically in Figure 6. The specimens were placed in the fixture and then tightly clamped at the ends. The specimens were supported laterally along the gauge length by lightly clamped aluminum plates to prevent the specimen from deflecting out-of-plane. A floor model TTDM Instron test machine was used. The tests were conducted at room temperature with dry specimens.

4.2 Determination of Unnotched Strength To determine the unnotched compression strength, a specimen with a variable cross-section was used (Figure 5a). The reason for reducing the cross-section in the gauge length is to prevent failure from occurring at the grips where the state of stress is multi-axial. In the specimen used, the failure will occur at the weakest section where stresses are uniaxial. By designing a large radius to the specimen, the influence of the stress concentration on the strength is relatively small.

The stress concentration factor at the weakest cross-section section of the specimens was estimated from the results of finite element analyses: 1.14 for laminate A specimens, 1.04 for laminate B specimens, and 1.06 for laminate C specimens.

The laminate compression strength was then determined as the mean value of the cross-section edge stress and the cross-section average stress, σ_a . The cross-section average stress, σ_a , was calculated:

$$\sigma_a = P/wt \quad (11)$$

where P is the ultimate failure load, w is the width at the weakest cross-section of the specimen, and t is the thickness of the laminate. Unnotched strengths were determined: 1243 MPa for laminate A, 581 MPa for laminate B, and 887 MPa for laminate C.

4.3 Determination of Critical Damage Zone Length To calculate the normalized strength of specimens containing circular holes according to the DZC, the critical damage zone length is required.

The critical length of the damage zone, d_{IC}^* , was calculated implicitly from Eq. (5) for laminates A, B, and C, by using the experimentally-determined strengths of small specimens ($w = 16$ and $2R = 4$ mm). The calculated critical lengths are: 1.75 mm for laminate A, 0.91 mm for laminate B, and 0.53 mm for laminate C.

4.4 Comparisons between the data and the model results The predicted strengths are presented in Table 2.

The predicted effect of hole diameter on the normalized strengths of laminate A, B, and C specimens is compared with experimental results in Figure 7-9. The ratio of hole diameter to specimen width was held constant at 1:4, with hole diameters of approximately 6, 12, and 16 mm and widths of 24, 48, and 64 mm. All specimens were 3.048 mm thick. The DZC provided results with very good accuracy.

5. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

The Damage Zone Criterion (DZC) is based on the physical reality that a damage zone will form and grow in the stress-intense region of the specimen. The stress redistribution following the damage development was taken into account. A closed form analytical expression of the notched strength was derived from the equilibrium conditions of the specimen. A consideration of the equilibrium of the specimen required that the stress distribution along the net-section plane be known. For simplicity, the stress distribution within the damage was assumed constant. The stress distribution ahead of the damage zone was assumed to have the same shape as the linear elastic stress distribution. The notched strength was predicted on the basis of the fundamental laminate parameters, σ_{oc} and d_{IC}^* .

The DZC has been evaluated with regard to its ability to predict in-plane compressive strength of composite laminates containing circular holes. The parameter d_{IC}^* of the criterion were determined from the experimental results of specimens with small circular holes, and used in predicting the strengths of specimens significantly larger circular holes. In general, the strengths predicted from the DZC agree very well with the experimental results. In addition to accuracy, the simplicity of the analytical approach, combined with its generality makes the DZC of practical value to the designer.

The DZC predicts fracture from a macroscopic point of view. Macroscopically, the fracture of laminates of different configurations are different, even though the laminates are fabricated from the same material system. Consequently, the fundamental parameters of the DZC must be determined for each individual laminate to be used in a design.

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Table 1. Laminate configurations.

Laminate	Stacking Sequence
A	$(\pm 45/0_4/90/0_2/90/0_2)_{S24}$
B	$(\pm 45/90_4/0/90_2/0/90_2)_{S24}$
C	$((\pm 45/0/90)_3)_{S24}$

where $S24$ defines a symmetric laminate with a total of 24 plies.

Table 2. Predicted strength of CH-specimens.

Laminate	d (mm)	w (mm)	t (mm)	$\sigma_N^{\text{EXP}}/\sigma_0$	$\sigma_N^{\text{DZC}}/\sigma_0$	Δ^{DZC} (%)
A	5.8	24.0	3.048	0.65	0.67	4
A	12.1	48.0	3.048	0.52	0.55	5
B	5.8	24.0	3.048	0.54	0.54	0
B	12.1	48.0	3.048	0.51	0.43	-15
B	16.1	64.0	3.048	0.48	0.40	-16
C	5.8	24.0	3.048	0.43	0.46	6
C	12.1	48.0	3.048	0.41	0.39	-4
C	16.1	64.0	3.048	0.40	0.38	-6

t Nominal laminate thickness.

σ_{oc} Unnotched compressive strength based on experimental average.

σ_N^{EXP} Experimental notched strength.

d Hole diameter.

w Specimen width.

Δ^{DZC} Deviation between predicted and experimental value: $\Delta^{\text{DZC}} = (\sigma_N^{\text{DZC}}/\sigma_N^{\text{EXP}} - 1)$.

FIGURE 1.

Failure modes of compressive loaded laminates [1]: (a) global buckling, Euler buckling or laminate buckling; (b) local buckling, sublaminates buckling or buckling of a ply or group of plies; (c) damage due to in-plane forces (such as fiber buckling and/or fiber shear crippling involving fiber kinking).

FIGURE 2.

Laminated composite plate containing a circular hole and subjected to compressive loading.

FIGURE 3.

Damage development ahead of a hole: (a) schematic of a compressive loaded specimen containing a circular hole; (b) damage initiation.

FIGURE 4.
Assumed stress distribution along the net-section plane prior to a failure.

FIGURE 5.
Geometry and dimensions of specimens: (a) unnotched specimen; (b) specimen containing a circular hole.

FIGURE 6.
Schematic of compression loading fixture.

FIGURE 7. Effect of hole diameter on the compression strength (laminate A). Comparisons between experimental data and predicted results.

FIGURE 8. Effect of hole diameter on the compression strength (laminate B). Comparisons between experimental data and predicted results.

FIGURE 9. Effect of hole diameter on the compression strength (laminate C). Comparisons between experimental data and predicted results.

BIOGRAPHY

The author received his MS in mechanical engineering from Linköping Institute of Technology (Sweden) and his PhD in light-weight structures from the Royal Institute of Technology, (Stockholm, Sweden). He has worked at Saab Aircraft Division for four years in research on bolted composite structures, among other things. He has also spend a couple of years as a visiting scholar at the Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics at Stanford University; and is presently assistant professor at the Department of Aeronautical Structures and Materials, at the Royal Institute of Technology.